

San Francisco International Airport

Analysis of the Impacts of SFO on the San Francisco and Bay Area Economies

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Introduction

San Francisco International Airport (SFO) is the largest and most heavily traveled airport in the greater Bay Area, serving 57.7 million passengers in 2018 alone. This is more than four times the number of passengers that flew through Oakland or San Jose airports. With those nearly 58 million passengers comes billions of dollars in tourism spending and business activity. This stimulates growth in the surrounding economy and facilitates the many industries which are located in San Francisco, the Bay Area, and Silicon Valley. SFO also operates as the largest shipping hub in Northern California, providing commercial fast shipping opportunities for hundreds of local manufacturers. SFO impacts the economy in San Francisco and the greater Bay Area in three significant ways: 1) Jobs and services supported directly and indirectly by foreign and domestic tourists and business travelers; 2) cargo and freight services, which support trade, (especially with Pacific Rim countries); and 3) intellectual property in the form of new ideas and skilled talent brought by industry professionals and entrepreneurs.

History of the Airport

In order to understand the current economic effect of SFO, it is important to understand the history behind the airport. San Francisco's location as one of the farthest western ports in the lower 48 meant it was on the leading edge for both sea shipping and later air shipping, especially due to the shorter travel distance to Asia. Although SFO is now the primary airport serving San Francisco, it was not the original airport serving the city. That distinction goes to Crissy Army Airfield which was built and run by the US Army Air Corps from 1921 to 1936, and then continued to operate as a military airstrip for passenger flights through 1974.

In 1926 the US Army was the primary service for air transport of mail across the country. As mail services grew, the Army requested that San Francisco build a larger airport and threatened to move operations to Sacramento if the city did not build a new airport by the end of 1926. Outraged at the possibility of San Francisco receiving their mail after Sacramento and the Central Valley, the citizens voted to build a new airport immediately. However, while the proposed airport had to meet certain criteria set by the city, the city planners did not say where the airport should be located. Some of the proposed locations included: on top of the Civic Center, along the Embarcadero, and even on the "Twin Peaks Plateau" (the location of which was never clear).

Eventually, it was decided that the airport would be built on a 150-acre plot of land which would become known as Mills Field Municipal Airport of San Francisco named after Ogden L. Mills, the owner of the land. Over the following 90 years, SFO was the location for numerous monumental events in civilian aviation history. It was given the classification of International Airport after World War II, and eventually become a hub for airlines such as United Airlines, which flew the first nonstop flights from coast to coast in 1954. Today San Francisco International Airport is the seventh-busiest airport in the United States and the 24th-busiest in the world, by passenger count.

Airport jobs and Passenger spending

San Francisco is a global tourist destination, as well as a meeting spot for many companies because of its ease of access for employees traveling from Asia. This results in San Francisco and the surrounding travel hubs profiting from the millions of yearly passengers who travel through the Bay Area. Once a traveler has arrived at a local port of entry in a new region they begin spending and continue to do so until they leave again. That spending pays the salaries of thousands of airport employees and supports regional transport, hotel, and other traveler-oriented services. Much of these employees' income is then re-spent at local businesses, resulting in a much larger group of companies benefitting indirectly from the tourists' spending. Re-spent income is income which an employee makes as a result of travelers paying for commodities and services within the airport. This income is then used to pay for employees' own livelihood in the local economy.

The Impact of Transit Passengers

Within the aviation industry, an airline will have one or more hubs from which they base their operations. This means that for any particular airline it will fly hundreds of flights through that airport, resulting in the airport becoming a major stopover location for passengers flying longer distances. This is known as a hub and spoke model, where each one of the spokes are individual flights out of the hub to other airports. SFO is a connection hub for many travelers for passengers flying from North America to Asia. An estimated 60% of passengers who use the airport, but do not have it as a destination or origin, come from outside of the greater Bay Area.

These passengers still buy products at airport shops and restaurants. Depending upon the time of year, San Francisco's notorious weather can cause delays, which can result in some passengers going into the cities around SFO. The delayed passengers will then purchase food, transportation, and sometimes hotel rooms. While delays may cost the airlines and travelers valuable time and money, many passengers choose to leave the airport and spend their money at surrounding businesses.

The Impact of Airport Employment

Most commercial flights require an army of people to get the plane off the ground. Once the designing and building of the aircraft are complete, there are ten different positions that an aircraft goes through from the time it arrives at a gate to the time it gets pushed back. As early as 1993, airlines

employed over 553,400 U.S. residents, including pilots, flight attendants, reservations and ticketing personnel, and mechanics, etc. [15]

The airport provides thousands of jobs, 3.5 thousand jobs provided by construction endeavors in 2017 alone, plus another 42 thousand on-site yearly. The largest sector of this is passenger airline services, which accounted for more than one-third of the employment at SFO. Another 33,300 jobs are sustained due to indirect or worker re-spending simply from the airport itself, in the local market. [3]

SFO provides the greater Bay Area directly and indirectly with upwards of 14.6 billion dollars in worker re-spending income [3]. Many of these workers are employed either directly or in close connection to the airport. In addition to the direct economic benefit of these jobs, these employees also spend their income elsewhere in the local economy, which further benefits the total economic growth of the region. Some of the revenue from airport sales is given to employees as salary which makes its way through the economic web to local businesses. This is how local businesses can be sustained by tourist activities, even if none of those tourists go to the business in person.

Worker re-spending added close to 20 thousand jobs to the local market, giving it an additional 3.76-million-dollar boost [3]. This is a common pattern with airports near many large metropolitan areas. For example, Heathrow Airport in London employs 50,000 people directly at the airport and at least 20,000 more in local businesses [11].

The Impact of Tourists and Business Travelers

When travelers visit a city, they stimulate the economy tremendously by staying in hotels, dining out at local restaurants, and using either public or private transportation in the area. These are just a few of the economic sectors that these travelers help to sustain, and the San Francisco Bay Area is no exception. Businesses will often fly hundreds of employees from around the world to cities such as San Francisco for conferences and conventions. In 2018, San Francisco hosted more than 25 major conventions or expositions. Some of the larger conventions, such as Salesforce.com's Dreamforce, had an estimated 60,000 attendees for their four-day event. The participants accounted for a total of nearly 132,600 hotel room nights (a five-night stay being 5 hotel room nights) [10].

Due in part to the vast number of visitors who visit the Bay Area each year, the airport is a vital gateway to the region and facilitates many of the tourism sectors of the local economy. 26% of these passengers are international, 12% are from California, and the remainder come from elsewhere in the United States. On average, international visitors spend about \$1,234 per trip, and domestic visitors spend a little less at \$1,024 per trip. The 10.5 billion dollars spent by nearly 10.2 million international and domestic visitors helps to support more than 138,000 jobs in the Bay Area alone [3].

San Francisco relies on the airport for the transportation of both tourists and business travelers. The airport provides San Francisco with 12,000 jobs in on-airport employment, while other counties such as San Mateo and Alameda receive 19,400 and 10,800 jobs, respectively. Visitor spending is another large sector for many counties. Alameda, Santa Clara, and San Francisco counties receive the most money from visitor spending, totaling over 13 billion dollars per year, more than 70% of the entire region's estimated visitor spending income[3].

Conclusion

Due to the number of passengers who travel to San Francisco and the Bay Area, it is no surprise that tourism and travelers are such a strong economic stimulant. Northern California is known for both its industry powerhouses and its natural and historical wonders. From the Golden Gate Bridge, an international landmark, and Yosemite National Park, one of the most well known national parks in the nation, to companies such as Apple or Google, it's no surprise that so many people come to the region. San Francisco International Airport is the largest airport serving the area and as a result, nearly every passenger who travels to any location in Northern California will spend money in San Francisco or the Bay Area. All of these passengers help to stimulate and grow the economy every year and will continue to do so into the future.

Cargo and freight

As with most major airports, San Francisco is a shipping center as well as a passenger airport. Most commercial flights, even if they are listed as passenger flights, carry some amount of cargo. Airlines will often sell out their extra cargo space to the highest bidder, or if they have an agreement with some other shipping service, will carry what they can on each flight. The extra weight in the aircraft means it burns more fuel and so costs the airline more to operate the flight. However, the incremental cost of fuel is far outweighed by the revenue and subsequent profit an airline makes when flying an aircraft with a full cargo hold. San Francisco is the largest air freight hub in Northern California, and generally one of the larger shipping centers in the region. SFO's ability to send vast amounts of cargo around the world in a fraction of the time it would take any other means makes it a very attractive option for many producers and suppliers. The air-freight industry stimulates the San Francisco and Bay Area economies by providing jobs in different sectors of shipping and gives new companies opportunities to expand their product line.

The Impact of International Trade

The Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP) was the centerpiece of President Barack Obama's strategic pivot to Asia and was set to become the world's largest free trade agreement. As a West Coast port of entry, SFO benefited greatly from the deal (eight of the top ten countries with over \$1 billion in trade through San Francisco are in Asia).

Although President Donald J. Trump withdrew the United States from the treaty in 2017, shipments nevertheless increased during the remainder of 2017 and 2018, with a 4.6% increase in cargo tonnage. This accounted for an additional 21,600 metric tons of cargo shipped through SFO in FY 2017 than FY 2016.

The local impact of air freight extends to a wide range of regional business sectors supporting many companies in the Bay Area. Given SFO's close proximity to Silicon Valley and its proven ability to transport vast amounts of cargo, it is no surprise that more than 83% of the total exports (by value) are in technological goods. These include electrical machinery, industrial machinery (including computers), and optics, with the majority of the remaining 17% spread across aircraft manufacturing, pharmaceutical products, chemicals, plastics, and other commodities and products.

The significant proportion of technological goods in the cargo total can be attributed to the many industries that manufacture their products in Asia and then send them to the US to their distribution centers. For some companies such as Apple, this amounts to billions of dollars in imports and exports each year.

SFO's Freight and Cargo Industries

San Francisco facilitates five major Cargo-only carriers, of which the top two are Atlas Air (more commonly known as DHL), and Federal Express (a.k.a. FedEx). In FY 2017-2018, SFO loaded and unloaded a total of over 571,000 metric tons of cargo. This included both Airmail and air freight, with domestic shipping accounting for 26% of the market share at 206,000 tons and the international market was dominated at 88% or roughly 365,000 tons [4].

There is, however, a growing pattern in which many shippers choose to transport their products via passenger carriers rather than Cargo-only air carriers. In FY 2018, Cargo-only air carriers' tonnage decreased by less than one percent, while cargo tonnage on passenger carriers increased by 32%. There are at least two possible explanations for this. One is that passenger carriers are offering more aggressive pricing prompting customers to use them, rather than Cargo-only air carriers. Another possibility is that Cargo-only air carriers are saturating their capacity and cannot easily grow to meet increasing demand. In any case, it is driving growth for both passenger and Cargo-only airlines.

SFO is also an equally large center for importing goods into the US from many major international companies. These range from clothing items produced across much of South-East Asia by companies such as Gap and H&M, to televisions, cellphones, and video games produced by technology companies located in Japan and Korea, such as Samsung and video game giant Softbank. SFO facilitates the import of 12.7 billion dollars in the categories of "Electric Machinery" and "Sound/TV Equipment". This includes personal computers and cell phones for individuals and accounts for 45% of SFO's imports by value. Domestic shipments also are dominated by technology with 65% of outbound air shipments from SFO originating in the electronics sector. SFO is not only a hub for the Bay Area, but for all of California. Somewhere between 38% and 58% of California's top three exported commodities are shipped through SFO [9].

The Impact of Air-Reliant Freight Industries

In total, over 20,000 jobs are dependent on Bay Area air-reliant businesses that purchase goods and services in order to make final products that are shipped via SFO [3]. More than half of the air-reliant businesses are in the service sector, and all of these businesses rely on SFO's capacity to efficiently and quickly ship thousands of tons of products around the world every day. Another 4,000 jobs are in the trade sector which uses SFO as both an international and domestic hub for shipping goods.

Many regional industries in Northern California have a strong reliance on consistent and rapid transportation of their products, which SFO satisfies each year. The airport facilitates the movement of products such as California almonds, which are shipped around the world and are known to be some of the best on the market. Edible fruits and nuts topped the list in 2016 at 28 thousand metric tons or 20% of the airport's total export. This only accounted for about 0.6% of the cargo value exported. Rail, freight

and conventional maritime shipping for these goods were neither consistent enough, nor provided the rapid shipping times that these products require [3].

Because of its location fairly centralized in California, SFO attracts producers from around the state, which often results in their shipping products to SFO by train or truck. Just as with tourism and business travelers, this supports a range of other businesses. Much of the air freight which arrives at SFO does not go straight to buyers and retail stores but rather goes to warehouses nearby to be broken up from their shipping pallets and then sent off to the individuals or stores. A quick online search finds over two dozen shipping companies in the San Francisco Bay Area which serve SFO. These companies often provide much more than simply shipping options around the Bay Area. Other services can range from storage options and redistribution of products to preparing shipments for international trade and customs brokerage and inspection.

Conclusion

San Francisco International Airport is just as much a cargo shipping center as a passenger airport. With so many local companies using the airport to ship goods around the world, there are numerous industries which would not be as vibrant in the Bay Area were it not for the shipping opportunities that SFO provides. Furthermore, the fast nature of air transport and the need for some products to go from producer to consumer in as little time as possible make SFO the obvious choice for international shipments. San Francisco International Airport supports the local economy considerably through the cargo services which are provided. This causes direct and indirect economic benefits to the Bay Area. The airport employs thousands of individuals for the movement and transfer of freight between aircraft and trucks. Numerous companies rely upon the airport in order to ship their products around the world, while others transport cargo to and from the airport, businesses and storage sites. The more air-freight shipped through the airport, the more people are employed and paid. These employees then re-spend their income at local businesses ultimately supporting economic growth in the region.

Supporting Innovation and Skilled Workforce

Within a one hour drive of San Francisco are some of the most profitable companies and two of the most reputable universities in the world. Five of the top 30 global Fortune 500 companies are located within 30 miles of SFO. The University of California, Berkeley and Stanford University, two of the top universities in the world, are both within a short commute from the airport. However many of these companies and research universities would not be as large and successful as they are today were it not for SFO. If a company wishes to become the best in their field they will generally have to look around the world to find the best talent. Airports make long-distance travel far easier and draw in bright minds in many different fields. An established innovation hub such as Silicon Valley draws in more people, but can only do so with easy access to international travel. All of these people moving in and out of the region for business have a strong positive impact on the local economy. Travelers coming through SFO need transportation, housing, and food, all of which is provided by Bay Area companies.

Who is in the Bay Area

San Francisco is known to be the birthplace of hundreds of start-up companies in almost every industry, from art and architecture to consulting and construction firms. One of the most prominent and successful sectors has been personal computers and consumer technology. It is not surprising to see that 28 of the world's Fortune 500 companies are located in the Bay Area. Apple, Google, Facebook, and Salesforce are just a few of the largest and most well-known technology companies in the Bay Area. Adobe and Oracle are known for their software, while others like Intel, Hewlett Packard and Western Digital are known for their hardware products. Bank of America, Wells Fargo and Visa, headquartered in downtown San Francisco and the peninsula, are providers for both the nation and the world's financial needs. Companies such as Chevron, McKesson, and PG&E provide the West Coast and the world with the needed products to keep many other industries running. These companies combined totaled over \$1 trillion in sales in FY 2016 [3 & 9].

Companies have statewide, western, national and even global business networks, requiring frequent and often international travel between various offices. Without the close proximity of SFO to these business centers, there is a high likelihood that more companies would leave the Bay Area. Over the past 9 years, none of the Fortune 500 companies in the region have left [3].

Local companies around the Bay Area use SFO as a vital connection point for travel in order to grow their operations while still remaining in one of the most technologically abundant regions in the world.

Economic Effects of Airports on Local Economies

San Francisco International Airport is a prime example of how an airport can affect a region's economy. Hooks, Makaryan, and Almeida said "Airports have a marked effect on economic growth. John Kasarda and his colleagues have shown a very strong correlation between U.S. metropolitan growth and air traffic (Irwin and Kasarda 1991; Kasarda and Sullivan 2006). What keeps this finding from being artifactual (since cities with a lot of economic activity generate a lot of traffic) is the hub system of American air transit, where hub cities get disproportionate amounts of fly-through traffic. It is precisely these hub cities with disproportionately large airports that receive the bonus rates of economic growth" [6].

High-tech manufacturing, knowledge-based service sectors, and agricultural industries rely on air service considerably more than other sectors for numerous reasons. Their passenger and cargo travel needs are driven by high-value, delicate and/or time-sensitive products requiring that they are shipped by air. Often it is not inanimate objects which hold the most value to companies, but rather the sale of professional expertise. Business and professional services often require that representatives of their companies travel around the world to meet with clients and make presentations.

The importance of international travel for business operations is reflected in company spending on flights. As one example, Apple was recently in the news for buying a staggering 50 business class seats per day to Shanghai on United flights, at a total cost of some 150 million dollars per year.

Airports draw in the best and brightest in their region and San Francisco International is no different. Unsurprisingly "Places with high levels of human capital enjoy fast economic growth and high productivity" [2]. San Francisco is just such an environment where the number of great minds all in close

proximity to one another means that the economy booms. Furthermore, “Button et al. (1999) found that proximity to an airport hub has important structural advantages for the local economy and showed that hubs create employment rather than follow employment trends” [1]. This is further reinforced by the idea that “Places without access to airports experience a deepening brain drain” and as also mentioned in [2] “Airports play an important role in attracting talent and places with high levels of talent/highly educated individuals enjoy robust economic growth and high productivity.” While this is more general in the analysis, it does encompass much of what San Francisco experiences as a result of its location in SFO.

Conclusion

Airports are just as much magnets for new people with new ideas to come to an area as they are travel hubs. The Bay Area economy draws a vast number of new people to the region. The influx of high-skilled and entrepreneurial employees is crucial for companies to come up with new products each year and to expand their operations. San Francisco tries to keep and entice companies to the Bay Area, however, were it not for local airports, in particular, SFO, it is likely that these companies would move elsewhere. The income that these companies generate through bringing new employees and innovative ideas to the Bay Area spread out across the entire local economy. SFO enables innovative companies around the Bay Area to expand, supporting the growth of high tech and other knowledge-based sectors. This has and will continue to make the San Francisco Bay Area region an economic powerhouse in the international economy.

Conclusion and Total Impact Summary

San Francisco International Airport, while not the largest or busiest airport in the world, is one of the most impactful. It is located near one of the world’s most important tech regions, with a huge number of companies headquartered in the Bay Area. This makes SFO the obvious option for millions of travelers per year. The airport is a valuable access point for both tourists and business people to visit, work in, or travel through the Bay Area.

With millions of passengers traveling through SFO each year, passenger spending adds millions to the Bay Area economy. This includes on-site airport employment, as well as the re-spending of employee income in the local market. Passengers from across the country and the world are bringing money into the local economy. This is then distributed across the Bay Area, impacting the entire region.

Freight and cargo transport also contribute hundreds of millions of dollars to the local Bay Area economy each year. This employs thousands of workers at the airport and in regional freight transport services. An additional impact comes as employees re-spend their income across different business sectors. With the number of new companies and start-ups in the Bay Area rising steadily each year, SFO’s role in facilitating product shipments continues to grow. This increase will continue to provide more jobs to the Bay Area.

In addition to the more obvious impacts of passenger spending, freight, and cargo transport, SFO’s impact also includes drawing in high-skilled workers and intellectual property. This helps maintain the Bay Area as a center for innovation, and provides a growing workforce for the booming technology

sector in Silicon Valley. The airport also provides an incentive for companies to remain in San Francisco, facilitating direct access to economies in Asia, Europe, and South America. This allows the Bay Area to retain its hold on some of the most lucrative markets in the world while still remaining a viable option for up-and-coming companies.

San Francisco International Airport plays a pivotal role in the larger economy of San Francisco. It will continue to provide income, employment and financial support for the surrounding counties for the foreseeable future. As aviation continues to grow as a business sector, so will SFO and so will the Bay Area economy.

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